

MATHEMATICAL FOUNDATIONS OF SEMANTIC SEARCH IN INTERNET ENGINES**Mammadov Eshgin***Master of Science in Computer Engineering (2nd year student)**Azerbaijan State Oil and Industrial University**16/21 Azadliq Ave, Baku, Azerbaijan***Abstract**

The advancement of semantic search algorithms relies heavily on the integration of sophisticated mathematical frameworks to decipher and interpret the semantics of user queries and web documents. This article provides an in-depth exploration of three key mathematical models utilized in semantic search: Vector Space Models (VSM), Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA), and Word Embeddings. Each model is meticulously examined, elucidating their mathematical foundations, operational principles, and integration into semantic search algorithms. From the mathematical representation of documents and queries in vector space to the application of Singular Value Decomposition (SVD) in uncovering latent semantic structures, the article delves into the intricacies of these models. Furthermore, it explores how Word Embeddings, exemplified by Word2Vec and GloVe, revolutionize semantic understanding through dense vector representations of words. By synthesizing these mathematical frameworks into semantic search algorithms, search engines can bridge the semantic gap between user intent and search results, ultimately enhancing the accuracy, relevance, and user experience of information retrieval. Through this nuanced analysis, the article underscores the indispensable role of mathematics in propelling the evolution of semantic search technology towards more intuitive and efficient information retrieval systems in the digital era.

Keywords: Semantic search algorithms, Mathematical frameworks, Vector space models, Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA), Word embeddings, Information retrieval

Introduction

Semantic search represents a paradigm shift in information retrieval systems, transcending traditional keyword-based search methodologies. Unlike conventional search engines that primarily rely on matching keywords, semantic search engines aim to understand the meaning behind user queries and the content of web documents. This understanding is facilitated by leveraging natural language processing (NLP) techniques, machine learning algorithms, and semantic analysis to interpret context, intent, and relationships within text data. Semantic search systems employ advanced algorithms to comprehend the nuances of language, enabling them to provide more relevant and accurate search results. By considering the semantics, or meanings, of words and phrases, these systems can infer the user's intent and deliver results that match the underlying concepts, even if the exact keywords are not present in the document.[2]

Mathematical foundations serve as the backbone of semantic search algorithms, providing the framework for modeling and analyzing the complex relationships inherent in language and information retrieval. These mathematical principles enable semantic search engines to process, represent, and compare textual data in a manner that captures its semantic essence.

Vector Space Models (VSM): At the core of many semantic search algorithms lies the concept of vector space models (VSM). VSM represents documents and queries as vectors in a high-dimensional space, where each dimension corresponds to a term in the vocabulary. By measuring the similarity between vectors, semantic search engines can rank documents based on their relevance to the user's query. The mathematical operations involved in VSM, such as cosine

similarity and term weighting, play a crucial role in determining the accuracy and effectiveness of semantic search results.

Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA): LSA is another mathematical framework commonly used in semantic search algorithms. It employs singular value decomposition (SVD) to uncover latent semantic structures within textual data. By reducing the dimensionality of the term-document matrix and capturing underlying patterns of word co-occurrence, LSA facilitates semantic similarity measurement and document retrieval. The mathematical principles behind SVD and its application in LSA are fundamental to understanding how semantic search engines extract semantic meaning from text.

Word Embeddings: Word embeddings have emerged as powerful mathematical models for representing words in a continuous vector space. Techniques such as Word2Vec and GloVe leverage neural networks to learn distributed representations of words based on their contextual usage. These word embeddings capture semantic relationships between words, enabling semantic search engines to understand semantic similarity and perform context-aware retrieval. The mathematical principles underlying the training and utilization of word embedding models are essential for optimizing semantic search performance.

In essence, the integration of mathematical principles into semantic search algorithms enables these systems to bridge the semantic gap between user queries and web documents, thereby enhancing the accuracy, relevance, and user experience of information retrieval. Through rigorous mathematical modeling and analysis, semantic search engines can decipher the intricate semantics of language and deliver meaningful search results that align with the user's information needs.

Understanding Semantic Search

Semantic search represents a significant advancement in the field of information retrieval, aiming to understand the meaning and context of user queries and documents. Unlike traditional keyword-based search engines, which match exact terms, semantic search engines employ sophisticated algorithms to comprehend the intent behind the user's query and the content of web documents. The evolution of semantic search can be traced back to the limitations of keyword-based approaches in capturing the nuances of human language and delivering relevant search results. Semantic search systems leverage various natural language processing (NLP) techniques, machine learning algorithms, and semantic analysis to interpret and analyze textual data. These systems aim to bridge the semantic gap between user queries and web documents by understanding the underlying concepts, entities, and relationships within the text. By considering the semantics of words and phrases, semantic search engines can provide more accurate and contextually relevant search results, enhancing the user experience and satisfaction.[1]

Semantic search algorithms consist of several key components that work together to process and analyze textual data, understand user queries, and retrieve relevant information. These components include:

1. **Text Preprocessing:** Before semantic analysis can take place, textual data undergoes preprocessing

steps such as tokenization, stop-word removal, stemming, and lemmatization to standardize and simplify the text.

2. **Semantic Analysis Techniques:** Semantic search algorithms employ various techniques such as vector space models (VSM), latent semantic analysis (LSA), word embeddings, and graph-based algorithms to extract semantic meaning from textual data. These techniques enable the algorithms to capture the context, semantics, and relationships within the text.

3. **Query Understanding:** Semantic search engines utilize advanced query understanding techniques to interpret the intent behind user queries. By analyzing the structure and semantics of the query, these engines can infer the user's information needs and formulate a more precise search strategy.

4. **Document Representation:** Documents are represented in a mathematical vector space, where each dimension corresponds to a term in the vocabulary. This vector representation enables semantic search engines to quantify the semantic similarity between queries and documents and rank them based on relevance.

5. **Ranking and Retrieval:** Semantic search algorithms rank documents based on their semantic similarity to the user's query. Techniques such as cosine similarity, PageRank, and graph-based algorithms are used to determine the relevance of documents and retrieve the most relevant ones for the user. [3]

Figure 1. High-level view of the activities of a Semantic Web search engine

Mathematical Frameworks in Semantic Search

• Vector Space Models (VSM)

Vector Space Models (VSM) are mathematical representations used to analyze and compare textual data in a high-dimensional vector space. In the context

of semantic search, VSM is employed to quantify the similarity between documents and queries based on the terms they contain. The fundamental idea behind VSM is to represent documents and queries as vectors, where each dimension corresponds to a term in the vocabulary. [4]

Figure 2. Vector representation of queries in VSM

Here’s a basic overview of how the VSM works:

1. Building a Document-Term Matrix: The first step in creating vector representations of documents involves setting up a Document-Term Matrix (DTM) or Term-Document Matrix (TDM). This matrix organizes documents in rows and terms (which can be words or phrases) in columns. Each cell in the matrix holds a number that reflects how often a term appears in a document or its relevance to that document.

2. Applying Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency (TF-IDF): Following the creation of the Document-Term Matrix (DTM), a common next step involves implementing a TF-IDF transformation on the raw term frequencies. TF-IDF, an acronym for Term Frequency-Inverse Document Frequency, serves as an index that gauges the relevance of a term within a specific document in comparison to its prevalence across the entire document collection. This method is instrumental in emphasizing significant terms and diminishing the weight of those that are frequently encountered across documents.

The Term-Frequency tf_{ij} is computed with respect to the i -th term and j -th document:

$$tf_{ij} = \frac{n_{ij}}{\sum_k n_{k,j}}$$

where n_{ij} are the occurrences of the i -th term in the j -th document.

The concept is based on the premise that if a document frequently mentions certain terms, it is likely focused on that particular subject matter. The Inverse-Document-Frequency idf_i takes into consideration the i -th terms and all the documents in the collection:

$$idf_i = \log \frac{|D|}{|d:t_i \in d|}$$

The underlying idea is that uncommon terms hold more significance than frequent ones: if a term appears

exclusively in one document, it may indicate that this term uniquely defines that document. The guiding principle suggests that infrequent terms carry more value than those commonly encountered: a term found exclusively within a single document may signify its distinctive characterization of that document. The calculation of the final score, $w_{i,j}$ for the i -th term in the j -th document, is derived through a straightforward multiplication: $tf_{ij} * idf_i$. Given that a document or query includes only a fraction of the total unique terms present in the corpus, the term frequency for many terms could be zero, indicating a need for a sparse vector representation to efficiently manage space requirements.

3. Vectorization: Following the application of TF-IDF or a comparable transformation, each document is then represented as a vector within a high-dimensional space. Typically, the length of these vectors is uniform, corresponding to the total count of unique terms in the corpus. However, the values assigned to each dimension will differ, reflecting the relative significance of each term within the specific document.

4. Cosine Similarity: To ascertain the degree of similarity between two vectors, $d1$ and $d2$ (which could represent a document/query pairing or a document/document comparison), cosine similarity is employed:

$$\cos(d1, d2) = \frac{d1d2}{||d1||d2||} = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^n d1_i d2_i}{\sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (d1_i)^2} \sqrt{\sum_{i=1}^n (d2_i)^2}}$$

This method measures the cosine of the angle between the two vectors, providing a metric that assesses their orientation in the vector space rather than their magnitude.

Figure 3. Cosine similarity between two vectors (d_1 and d_2)

Let's examine a straightforward illustration of the Vector Space Model (VSM) employing a compact corpus of documents alongside a query. In this scenario, documents and a query will be conceptualized as vectors, and through the calculation of cosine similarity, we aim to identify and retrieve documents pertinent to the query. [5]

To employ the Vector Space Model (VSM) for information retrieval, we begin with a simple setup involving a corpus of three documents and a specific query ("brown dog"). We illustrate the process as follows:

1. **Corpus Composition:** Our corpus includes:
 - Document 1: "The quick brown fox jumps over the lazy dog."
 - Document 2: "A brown dog chased the fox."
 - Document 3: "The dog is lazy."
2. **Document-Term Matrix (DTM) Creation:** We construct a DTM using TF-IDF values, where each row represents a document and each column a term. The TF-IDF values quantify the importance of each term within the documents relative to the corpus.

Table 1.

Document -Term Matrix for VSM

Term	Doc 1	Doc 2	Doc 3	Query
a	0	0.41	0	0
brown	0.29	0.29	0	0.71
chased	0	0.41	0	0
dog	0.29	0.29	0.41	0.71
fox	0.29	0.29	0	0
is	0	0	0.41	0
jumps	0.29	0	0	0
lazy	0.29	0	0.41	0
over	0.29	0	0	0
quick	0.29	0	0	0
the	0.58	0.41	0.41	0

3. **Query Vectorization:** The query "brown dog" is also vectorized using a binary scheme, indicating the presence (1) or absence (0) of terms from the DTM.

Table 2.

Query Vectorization for VSM

Term	Query
a	0
brown	1
chased	0
dog	1
fox	0
is	0
jumps	0
lazy	0
over	0
quick	0
the	0

4. Cosine Similarity Calculation: We calculate the cosine similarity between the query vector and each document vector to determine relevance. The cosine similarity scores are as follows:

- Document 1: ~0.58
- Document 3: ~0.41
- Document 2: ~0.29

5. Document Ranking by Similarity: Documents are ranked based on their cosine similarity to the query, in descending order. Therefore, Document 1, with the highest similarity (~0.58), is deemed most relevant to the query "brown dog," followed by Document 3 and Document 2.

The issue of vector normalization introduces a nuanced challenge: shorter documents that concentrate on a single topic may be unduly favored over longer documents covering multiple topics, as the normalization process does not account for document length. Pivoted normalization addresses this by adjusting the relevance of documents based on their length compared to an empirically determined pivot length l_p . Documents shorter than this pivot length are deemed less relevant, while those exceeding the pivot length are considered more relevant, as illustrated by the concept of "Pivoted Normalization."

Figure 4. Pivoted normalization vs standard normalization

• **Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA)**

Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) is a mathematical technique used to uncover latent semantic structures within textual data. It is based on the principle that words that appear in similar contexts tend to have similar meanings. LSA aims to capture the underlying semantic relationships between words and documents by representing them in a lower-dimensional semantic space.

Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA) operates on the foundation of the Bag of Words (BoW) model, culminating in the generation of a term-document

matrix that captures the frequency of terms across documents. Within this matrix, rows are designated for terms, while columns correspond to individual documents. LSA uncovers latent topics by executing a matrix decomposition on the term-document matrix through Singular Value Decomposition (SVD). Predominantly, LSA is employed as a technique for dimensionality reduction or for mitigating noise within the data.[6]

Figure 5. Term-document matrix used in Latent Semantic Analysis

At the heart of LSA lies Singular Value Decomposition (SVD), a matrix factorization technique used to decompose a matrix into three matrices: U , Σ , and V^T . Given a term-document matrix A , where each row represents a document and each column represents a term, SVD decomposes A as follows:

$$A = U \Sigma V^T$$

Where:

- U is an $m \times n$ orthogonal matrix representing the left singular vectors.
- Σ is an $n \times n$ diagonal matrix containing the singular values in descending order.
- V is a $m \times n$ right singular matrix
- V^T is $n \times m$ matrix, which is the transpose of the V .

Once the term-document matrix has been decomposed using SVD, LSA performs dimensionality reduction by retaining only the top k singular values and their corresponding singular vectors. This process transforms the original term-document matrix into a lower-dimensional semantic space, where each document and term is represented as a vector. To compute the similarity between documents or between a query and a document in the semantic space, LSA calculates the cosine similarity between their corresponding vectors. The cosine similarity measure quantifies the similarity between two vectors by computing the cosine of the angle between them.

$$similarity(d_i, d_j) = \frac{d_i \cdot d_j}{\|d_i\| \|d_j\|}$$

Where:

- d_i and d_j are the vectors representing documents i and j in the semantic space.
- $\|d_i\|$ and $\|d_j\|$ represent the Euclidean norms of the document vectors.

LSA plays a crucial role in semantic search algorithms by capturing the latent semantic relationships between words and documents. By reducing the dimensionality of the term-document matrix and uncovering hidden semantic factors, LSA enables semantic search engines to better understand the underlying meaning of textual data. [7]

• **Word Embeddings**

Word embeddings are dense vector representations of words in a continuous vector space, where each word is mapped to a high-dimensional vector. Unlike traditional one-hot encoding, where each word is represented as a sparse vector with only one element being 1 and all others 0, word embeddings capture semantic relationships between words based on their contextual usage. Words with similar meanings or usages tend to have similar vector representations, enabling algorithms to leverage these embeddings to understand and process natural language more effectively.

Figure 6. Structure of vector search used with word embeddings

Two popular mathematical models for generating word embeddings are Word2Vec and GloVe (Global Vectors for Word Representation).

1. **Word2Vec**

Developed by Tomas Mikolov and his team at Google in 2013, Word2Vec is a technique for embedding words that addresses complex NLP challenges. It processes vast amounts of text to identify word associations or dependencies.

Word2Vec evaluates word similarities through the cosine similarity metric. A cosine similarity of 1 indicates identical words, while a 90-degree angle

suggests no contextual relation between words. It assigns similar vectors to words with similar meanings.

Word2Vec introduces two neural network models: Continuous Bag of Words (CBOW) and Skip-gram. CBOW predicts a target word based on context words, making it efficient for frequent word representations. Skip-gram, in contrast, predicts context words from a single input word, effectively capturing rare word representations. Both models excel at identifying semantic relationships, such as the association between countries and their capitals, aiding in semantic analysis applications like recommendation systems and knowledge exploration. [8]

Figure 7. CBOW & Skip-gram architectures

2. GloVe

Developed by Jeffrey Pennington and colleagues at Stanford, GloVe stands out by enhancing Word2Vec's methodology to encompass global contextual insights within a text corpus. This is achieved by calculating a global word-word co-occurrence matrix, which contrasts with Word2Vec's focus on local word contexts.

Unlike Word2Vec, which limits context capture to adjacent words during training, GloVe broadens this scope to the entire corpus, constructing a comprehensive matrix that details word co-occurrences throughout the text.

GloVe marries the benefits of two distinct approaches to word vector development: the matrix factorization approach, exemplified by latent semantic analysis (LSA), and the local context window technique, as seen in Skip-gram. It simplifies the training process with a more straightforward least square cost function, thus optimizing computational efficiency. The resulting word embeddings from GloVe offer enhancements and variations compared to those generated by Word2Vec. In tests like word analogy and named entity recognition, GloVe has shown superior performance, surpassing Word2Vec in certain tasks while holding competitive in others. Both methods, however, excel at capturing semantic nuances within a corpus.

Figure 8. GloVe word vectors capturing words with similar semantics.

Word embeddings are integrated into semantic search algorithms to enhance their understanding of natural language semantics. In semantic search, word embeddings are used to represent both queries and documents in a continuous vector space. Semantic similarity between queries and documents is computed using cosine similarity or other distance metrics on their corresponding word embedding vectors. By leveraging word embeddings, semantic search algorithms can capture subtle semantic relationships between words and improve the relevance of search results. Additionally, word embeddings enable semantic search engines to

handle out-of-vocabulary words and better understand the context of user queries, leading to more accurate and contextually relevant search results. [9]

Conclusion

In this article, we have explored the intricate mathematical frameworks that underpin semantic search algorithms, focusing on Vector Space Models (VSM), Latent Semantic Analysis (LSA), and Word Embeddings. These mathematical models play a pivotal role in enhancing the effectiveness and accuracy of modern internet search engines by enabling them to understand the semantics of user queries and web documents.

Vector Space Models provide a foundation for representing textual data in a high-dimensional space, facilitating the computation of similarity between documents and queries. Latent Semantic Analysis leverages Singular Value Decomposition to uncover latent semantic structures within textual data, enabling semantic search engines to capture the underlying semantic relationships between words and documents. Word Embeddings, such as Word2Vec and GloVe, offer dense vector representations of words in a continuous vector space, allowing algorithms to capture semantic relationships between words based on their contextual usage.

By integrating these mathematical frameworks into semantic search algorithms, search engines can deliver more accurate, relevant, and contextually rich search results to users. Through the application of VSM, LSA, and Word Embeddings, semantic search engines can bridge the semantic gap between user queries and web documents, enabling them to understand the nuances of human language and provide more meaningful search experiences.

As the field of semantic search continues to evolve, further advancements in mathematical modeling and analysis will undoubtedly drive improvements in search engine technology. By embracing the interdisciplinary synergy between mathematics and computer science, researchers can continue to push the boundaries of semantic search, ultimately enhancing the accessibility and usability of information on the internet for users worldwide.

References

1. Jain R, Duhan N, Sharma AK. Comparative Study on Semantic Search Engines. Vol. 131, International Journal of Computer Applications. Foundation of Computer Science; 2015. p. 4–11.
2. d'Aquin M, Ding L, Motta E. Semantic Web Search Engines [Internet]. Handbook of Semantic Web Technologies. Springer Berlin Heidelberg; 2011. p. 659–700.
3. Kamath SS, Piraviperumal D, Meena G, Karkidholi S, Kumar K. A semantic search engine for answering domain specific user queries [Internet]. 2013 International Conference on Communication and Signal Processing. IEEE; 2013.
4. Turney PD, Pantel P. From Frequency to Meaning: Vector Space Models of Semantics [Internet]. Vol. 37, Journal of Artificial Intelligence Research. AI Access Foundation; 2010. p. 141–88.
5. Hadi SM, Alsaeedi AH, Al-Shammary D, Alkareem Alyasseri ZA, Mohammed MA, Abdulkareem KH, et al. Trigonometric words ranking model for spam message classification [Internet]. IET Networks. Institution of Engineering and Technology (IET); 2022.
6. Landauer TK, Foltz PW, Laham D. An introduction to latent semantic analysis [Internet]. Vol. 25, Discourse Processes. Informa UK Limited; 1998. p. 259–84.
7. Mavridis T, Symeonidis AL. Semantic analysis of web documents for the generation of optimal content [Internet]. Vol. 35, Engineering Applications of Artificial Intelligence. Elsevier BV; 2014. p. 114–30.
8. Mikolov T, Chen K, Corrado G, Dean J. Efficient Estimation of Word Representations in Vector Space [Internet]. arXiv; 2013.
9. Pennington J, Socher R, Manning C. Glove: Global Vectors for Word Representation [Internet]. Proceedings of the 2014 Conference on Empirical Methods in Natural Language Processing (EMNLP). Association for Computational Linguistics; 2014